

Contributions of the 5th Industrial Revolution and How the Third and Fourth Industrial Revolutions Differ

¹Umar Baban Turai, ²Abdulkadir Shehu Bari, ³Abdulrazaq Abdulaziz, ⁴Muhammad Ahmad Baballe*

¹Nigeria Special Constabulary Police, Kano State Command, Nigeria.

²Department of Computer Science, Audu Bako College of Agriculture Danbatta, Kano, Nigeria.

³Department: Electrical and Electronics Engineering, University: Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Mechatronics Engineering, Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA), Kaduna, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: [Muhammad Ahmad Baballe](mailto:muhammad.ahmad.baballe@nada.gov.ng)

Department of Mechatronics Engineering, Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA), Kaduna, Nigeria.

ORCID: 0000-0001-9441-7023

Abstract

Industry 4.0, commonly referred to as the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), is transforming the globe through its rapid technological advancements and everyday integration of cutting-edge digital technologies. This revolution drives significant breakthroughs in engineering, business, manufacturing, and technology, building on previous industrial stages. Along with its many benefits—such as enhanced productivity, economic growth, improved quality of life, informed decision-making, and sustainability—industry 4.0 also has some serious drawbacks. These include growing inequality, rising cybercrime, reliance on technology, AI-driven employment displacement, and privacy issues. This study examines the contradictions of Industry 4.0, emphasizing the need for balance to ensure that technological growth serves humanity. The study encourages the application of technology to improve societal well-being, human flourishing, and fair economic progress. This study has discussed the differences between the third and fourth industrial revolutions as well as the contributions of the fifth (5IR) industrial revolution. Contributions of the 5th Industrial Revolution and How the Third and Fourth Industrial Revolutions Differ.

Keywords: Third Industrial Revolution (3IR), Digital Globalization, Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), Digital Transformation, Internet of Things (IoT), Fifth Industrial Revolution (5IR).

I. INTRODUCTION

The Fourth Industrial Revolution and its Impact on the Development of the High-Tech World. Today, a new phase of the scientific and technological revolution is coming with the relocation of the world's industrial, manufacturing, and scientific centers. The Fourth Industrial Revolution, which includes three areas, such as information, physics, and biology, is changing its shape. Technological innovations include global collaboration, digital capabilities and acceleration, and use of basic research facilities and equipment. The 2030s will require a strong scientific and technological nation and scientific and technical talent, which will be expanded with new discoveries, technologies, and scientific and technical talent that are more diversified and internationalized in the context of the development of digital transformation of education in the European Union [4]. The concept of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which is already evolving to 5G, has extremely significant and far-reaching implications. In recent years, technological advances such as next-generation information, new materials, new power, and life sciences have continuously given rise to emerging industries, and transformative sectors such as artificial intelligence (AI) and blockchain have developed rapidly. The concept of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) has been increasingly recognized by all segments of society and has also gradually gained attention. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) affects technological innovation, social progress, and economic development in a comprehensive manner, as well as talent demand, especially scientific and technological ones. The new conditions of globalization, modernization, and internal contradictions of the knowledge and technology systems are giving rise to a new round of scientific and technological revolution characterized by environmental

friendliness, intelligence, and omnipresence. As a result of these processes, there is a profound expansion of information technology, biotechnology, new material technologies, and new power technologies, which are contributing to the emergence of new digital innovations. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) is the embodiment of the scientific and technological revolution in its industrial transformation, which is evolving into the Fifth. Dominant technologies are emerging in the form of technology clusters, including next-generation information technologies, new energy technologies, low-carbon green technologies, and life sciences. Interdisciplinary integration and development are affecting people's cognitive structure and working methods. Major breakthroughs in interdisciplinary issues require new demands on systems thinking and teamwork. The frontier fields are constantly expanding, and materials science is evolving towards micro-depth, macro-extension, and extreme conditions. Digital breakthroughs are occurring in major scientific fields such as the structure of matter, the evolution of the universe, the origin of life, and the nature of mind, which require the development of smart education and smart business [5]. The development of a new generation of information technology and equipment industry directly affects the way of scientific research and innovation. The development of neurocognitive science contributes to a deeper understanding of cognitive models, which has a positive impact on the progress and breakthroughs in other areas. The actual needs of the ecological civilization are contributing to major breakthroughs in many fields of technology. A significant part of people's quest for a better life is the desire for a better ecological environment. Previous scientific advances and technological revolutions have brought human progress to unprecedented heights but also caused many deep-rooted environmental problems. A significant part of creating a new stage of the scientific and technological revolution is to meet the real needs of improving the ecological environment and to achieve harmonious coexistence between humans and nature, which will be one of the important components of the current stage of the digital revolution.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this paper, we explore the literature on the evolution of the Industrial Revolution as well as the characterization of each phase. The characterization forms part of the foundation towards the development of a comprehensive body of knowledge on the Digital Industrial Revolution as well as its evolution over the years in tandem with the Industrial Revolution. The outcome of the body of knowledge is to establish a foundation for a broader study on the socio-economic dynamics of the Digital Industrial Revolution and how such dynamics can be exploited for socio-economic development in Africa [1]. This research will provide academics with a better knowledge of evolution theory and digital leadership and recommendations for additional research on must-have issues to gain a better knowledge of digital leadership in the public sector throughout the industry. 4.0 transformation [2]. The article analyzes the fifth generation of 5G mobile telecommunication systems, which is a new wireless communication standard that will bring significant improvements in the data transfer speed of connecting many devices simultaneously [3]. This revolution also brings challenges, such as the need for project managers to continuously update their skills and resistance to cultural change within organizations. To adapt, it is essential to invest in digital training and agile methodologies. Recent studies highlight that the proliferation of technologies such as robotics, AI, and big data is transforming the job market and requiring new competencies. Research also shows how 5G and IoT are transforming industrial applications, necessitating new decentralized communication mechanisms. In summary, the Fourth Industrial Revolution presents a landscape full of opportunities for innovation and efficiency, but it requires project managers to develop new approaches and adapt to the demands of a constantly changing environment [6]. This paper presents the first integration of industrial digital models with a 5G digital model, implemented as an Asset Administration Shell (AAS) of a 5G system. The two models are interconnected using an OPC-UA-based interface. We evaluate the impact of the integrated model using a use case where automated guided vehicles (AGVs) transport material from a warehouse to production lines. The AGVs periodically exchange their positions over 5G to avoid potential collisions. If the communications fail, the AGVs stop for safety reasons until a reliable 5G connection can be guaranteed. We demonstrate that, by integrating 5G and industrial digital models, it is possible to account for and quantify the impact of 5G communications on the operation and productivity of industrial processes. This result highlights the importance and necessity of integrating 5G into industrial digital models for their joint design and optimization [7]. This research delineates specific technological, policy, and social challenges constraining 5G's change potential across contexts. It also compiles exemplary interventions by regulators, operators, and civil society promoting efficient and responsible rollouts. Our findings highlight urgent imperatives for collaborative action on standards, spectrum cooperation, security frameworks, and digital inclusion if 5G is to foster inclusive prosperity. We propose evidence-based and context-specific policy and investment recommendations tailored to local institutional realities while upholding ethical principles. By elucidating high-potential spaces for 5G innovation alongside risks of technological fragmentation, uneven access, and unintended consequences, this research provides a multidimensional decision-support framework for policymakers, regulators, operators, and enterprise leaders invested in promoting digitally enabled growth. It combines rigorous longitudinal data analysis with social impact forecasting to promote 5G ecosystems that responsibly widen opportunity and safeguard the interests of marginalized communities. The study sets the agenda for continued scholarship at the intersection of next-generation infrastructure investment, productivity growth in core economic sectors, and equitable expansion of digital capability sets across societies [8]. This paper investigates the security challenges associated with various access technologies, such as Fiber to the Home (FTTH), 4G, 5G, and broadband connections, in the context of Software-Defined Wide Area Network

(SD-WAN) deployments [9]. This article presents the architecture and implementation of the industrial internet identification and resolution system of a digital learning factory driven by 5G. This article also elaborates on the design of digital asset management training courses in the Advanced Manufacturing Technology Center (AMTC). This study seeks to advance the continuous improvement of digital module platforms within learning factories and foster the development of compound engineering talents through relevant theories and technologies in fully connected digital learning factories. The objective is to establish a benchmark that will stimulate further exploration in the direction of digital-intelligent, environmentally sustainable, and integrated industrial transformation and enhancement [10]. In the realm of digital manufacturing workshops, Huang et al. [11] introduced a real-time localization platform designed for various elements within discrete manufacturing environments. This platform integrates area localization techniques based on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and Ultra-Wide Band (UWB) precision localization methods. Segura et al. [12] explored the potential of employing an Internet of Things (IoT) tag system in the fabrication and assembly of crankshafts to capture and transmit production data. Cao et al. [13] presented a collaborative framework for tracking materials and production processes from a supply chain perspective, leveraging IoT tags and information technology (IT) systems to gather real-time production data. However, there remains a lack of uniformity in asset identification research across workshops, factories, industry chains, and even cloud platform manufacturing.

III. THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE THIRD AND FOURTH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION

1. Decentralised Information

Nowadays, sensors that gather a constant flow of data are found in many parts of the production process. In Industry 3.0, all of the data from a single system is often stored and managed on the local servers of each enterprise. There was very little cross-sector integration and data sharing. On the other hand, Industry 4.0 is the exact opposite. Multiple stakeholders can access data in real time because of its interconnected platforms and systems.

2. Real-Time Data Collection

In real time, enormous amounts of data are being collected, processed, and used. There are various benefits to having decentralized information available and able to analyze it instantly. It facilitates better decision-making by facilitating more efficient collaboration between various organizations and aiding in the optimization of production and management operations. Predictive maintenance is one strategy that significantly lowers downtime.

3. Big Data Analytics

Operational efficiency has been significantly impacted by big data. Numerous facets of manufacturing and business considerations, including consumer feedback and refunds, can now be examined and evaluated. Reducing outages, anticipating future demands, and improving decision-making are all made possible by these and numerous other contributing factors. Businesses can adjust to the demands of the market thanks to big data.

4. AI And ML

Humans cannot handle the enormous amount of intelligent data gathered in today's operations. The AI and ML algorithms of Industry 4.0 have supplanted the data analysts of Industry 3.0. These systems are not only capable of handling large amounts of data, but they can also learn from its analysis how to enhance automation in all its forms. Overall efficiency, quality, and production all improve as a result. By combining automation and intelligence, Industry 4.0 makes it possible for machines and systems to become more intelligent, self-sufficient, and adaptable.

5. Interoperability

Significant manufacturing technological advancements were made by Industry 3.0, although its primary goal was process automation. Additionally, it was limited to specific companies, each of which had its own systems. Connectivity and cooperation across business ecosystem stakeholders are key components of Industry 4.0. Manufacturers, their clients, suppliers, and even the equipment themselves may be among them. The goal is to encourage "collective intelligence" among organizations that exchange information and ideas in order to spur innovation and progress. As a result, various value chain elements work together in an ecosystem that is fully transparent, communicates easily, and is interoperable.

6. Heightened Flexibility

Lean production was embraced by Industry 3.0, which reduced costs by automating and optimizing procedures. Instead, Industry 4.0 is focused on brilliant production, where data, not expertise, is used to make decisions. Without human input, automated systems make predictions and optimize operations by learning from the collected data. Different methods are being used to generate new revenue streams. In this case, systems are linked to the product rather than the process. They are improving the responsiveness and flexibility of industrial processes. This enables them to respond to shifting consumer needs and market conditions more effectively and quickly.

So, How Does Industry 4.0 Differ from Industry 3.0?

Industry 3.0 achieved limited technological advances in manufacturing with computers, automation, and PLCs. Industry 4.0 leverages far more advanced technologies through the IIoT, cloud computing, augmented reality, and robotics. Add to these AI, ML, and big data analytics, and you have real-time connectivity, autonomous systems, predictive maintenance,

and data-driven decision-making. In addition, the physical and virtual worlds can be merged to enhance many design and manufacturing processes.

Industry 3.0 was all about automation in individual factories. It aimed to save money by improving efficiency and productivity. It optimized production lines by substituting machines and computers for human labor. Industry 4.0 has a much broader scope, integrating digital technologies into the value chain. Interconnected CPS can even manage distribution and customer interaction. This makes the digital transformation of the industry far more comprehensive. We're in a major shake-up of how things work, not just processes but business models and value creation. As Industry 4.0 gathers momentum, we need new skills for the latest technologies. At this stage, we need digital capabilities to be integrated into every organizational aspect of a business [19].

IV. BENEFITS OF THE FOURTH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION

1. **Enhanced Efficiency:** Productivity is increased and resource waste is decreased when smart technologies are integrated into manufacturing and other industries.
2. **Economic Growth:** Industry 4.0-driven innovation has the potential to generate new industries and business models, which will promote economic growth.
3. **Better Quality of Life:** Technological developments can result in smarter cities, better healthcare, and improved services, all of which can improve people's quality of life.
4. **Better Decision-Making:** Real-time data analytics aid in making informed decisions, optimizing business strategies and operations.
5. **Sustainability:** Smart technologies that maximize resource use and minimize environmental impact support sustainability.

V. Drawbacks of the Fourth Industrial Revolution

- a. **Job displacement:** AI and automation may make human labor less necessary, especially for physical and repetitive tasks, which would result in joblessness.
- b. **Increased Inequality:** Income and social imbalances may worsen as a result of Industry 4.0's potential for unequal distribution of benefits.
- c. **Cybersecurity Risks:** The interconnectedness of devices and systems heightens vulnerability to cyberattacks, posing risks to individual and public safety.
- d. **Privacy Issues:** The extensive collection and analysis of data can infringe on personal privacy if not managed with robust protections.
- e. **Technological Dependency:** If vital systems are interrupted, an excessive dependence on digital technology may lead to vulnerabilities [14].

VI. 5th Industrial Revolution Examples

The 5th Industrial Revolution, while still a conceptual phase, focuses on the integration of human ingenuity and creativity with advanced technologies, aiming for a more sustainable and human-centric approach. Here are some hypothetical examples that illustrate what the 5th Industrial Revolution might encompass:

1. **Collaborative Robotics (Cobots):**
Unlike traditional robots that operate independently, cobots [23-24] work alongside humans, enhancing their capabilities rather than replacing them. For instance, a cobot in a manufacturing setting could assist workers by handling heavy lifting or precision tasks, reducing strain and increasing productivity while keeping the human worker in control.
2. **Personalized Medicine:**
Leveraging advancements in genomics, AI, and biotechnology, personalized medicine in the 5th Industrial Revolution could tailor medical treatments to individual patients. This approach not only improves healthcare outcomes but also focuses on the human aspect of medical care, emphasizing patient-centric solutions.
3. **Sustainable Manufacturing:**
Integrating advanced technologies with a commitment to sustainability, manufacturing processes could become more efficient and less wasteful. For example, using AI and IoT for real-time monitoring and optimization of energy use in factories, or employing 3D printing to reduce material waste and enable local production, minimizing the carbon footprint.
4. **Smart Cities:**
Urban environments where technology and human-centric design converge to create more livable, sustainable, and inclusive communities. Smart cities in the 5th Industrial Revolution would use IoT, AI, and big data to improve urban infrastructure, public services, and quality of life, focusing on enhancing the human experience in the urban landscape.

5. Ethical AI:

Development and implementation of AI systems that prioritize ethical considerations, transparency, and accountability, ensuring that technology aligns with human values and societal well-being. This could involve frameworks and regulations that guide the ethical use of AI, emphasizing its role in supporting and augmenting human capabilities rather than undermining them.

These examples embody the vision of the 5th Industrial Revolution, where technology serves humanity, fostering a symbiotic relationship that enhances human capabilities, prioritizes ethical considerations, and promotes a sustainable future.

The 5th Industrial Revolution Summary

The 5th Industrial Revolution is envisioned as an era where technology and humanity coalesce to foster a more inclusive, sustainable, and human-centric global economy. It builds on the digital transformation of the 4th Industrial Revolution but emphasizes the reintegration of human intuition and values into technological advancements. This revolution highlights the importance of collaboration between humans and machines, focusing on enhancing human capabilities rather than replacing them, and prioritizes sustainable practices and ethical considerations in technological development. The goal is to leverage advanced technologies to address societal challenges, improve quality of life, and ensure that the benefits of technological progress are equitably distributed.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study recommends the following strategies for individuals to thrive in the Fourth Industrial Revolution: upskill and reskill in emerging technologies, engage in lifelong learning through continuous training and retraining, leverage digital platforms for entrepreneurship, adopt remote work and flexible schedules, utilize AI-powered tools for personalized learning, and develop skills in Python, Java, AI, IoT, and big data [20].

For businesses, the study suggests undergoing digital transformation through adopting digital technologies, fostering innovation through research and development, making data-driven decisions using analytics and machine learning, investing in robust cybersecurity measures, cultivating collaborative ecosystems with startups, academia, and governments, and focusing on innovative technologies like Artificial Intelligence, IoT, cloud computing, virtual and augmented reality, blockchain, and 5G/6G. By embracing these opportunities, individuals and businesses can thrive in the Fourth Industrial Revolution and pave the way for the technological singularity era [22].

REFERENCE

1. Ramugondo, N., Ngassam, E.K., Singh, S. (2023). On the Characterization of Digital Industrial Revolution. In: Silhavy, R., Silhavy, P. (eds) Artificial Intelligence Application in Networks and Systems. CSOC 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 724. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-35314-7_64.
2. Yuliza, Muafi, Handari Wahyuningsih, S. (2024). The Industrial Revolution 4.0 and Digital Leadership in the Public Services Sector. In: Khamis Hamdan, R., Hamdan, A., Alareeni, B., Khoury, R.E. (eds) Information and Communication Technology in Technical and Vocational Education and Training for Sustainable and Equal Opportunity. Technical and Vocational Education and Training: Issues, Concerns and Prospects, vol 39. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-7798-7_6.
3. Valentyna V., "Digital Technology Evolution of the Industrial Revolution From 4G to 5G in the Context of the Challenges of Digital Globalization", TEM Journal. Volume 12, Issue 2, pages 732-742, ISSN 2217-8309, DOI: 10.18421/TEM122-17, May 2023.
4. Andriukaitiene, R., Voronkova, V., Nikitenko, V. "The concept of digital transformation of education in the countries of the European Union: The European experience / European vector of economic modernization in the conditions of sustainable development of the industrial region", 2021. P. 72-86.
5. Voronkova, V., Nikitenko, V. "Smart education in the digital age: from smart education to smart business", Edukacja i Społeczeństwo VII, 268- 276, 2022.
6. Luis J. N. D., "Digital transformation in the fourth industrial revolution: Challenges and opportunities for project management", Revista Científica Sistemática, São José dos Pinhais, V.14, N.º 5, Set., 2024.
7. J. Cañete-Martín, et al., "Integration of 5G and Industrial Digital Models: A Case Study with AGVs", Proc. of 2024 IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (IEEE ETFA 2024), Sept. 2024.
8. Shaji G. A., "5G-Enabled Digital Transformation: Mapping the Landscape of Possibilities and Problems", Partners Universal Innovative Research Publication (PUIRP), Volume: 02 Issue: 03, May-June 2024, www.puirp.com.
9. Shaji G. A., Hovan A. S. G, Baskar T., "SD-WAN Security Threats, Bandwidth Issues, SLA, and Flaws: An In Depth Analysis of FTTH, 4G, 5G, and Broadband Technologies", Partners Universal International Innovation Journal (PUIIJ), Volume: 01 Issue: 03, May-June 2023, www.puiij.com.

10. Xinzhe Z, Weimin Z., Ziwei J., “Asset Management of Digital Learning Factory Driven by 5G Based on Industrial Internet Identification and Resolution Technology”, *Academic Journal of Science and Technology*, Vol. 12, No. 2, 2024.
11. Segura Velandia D M, Kaur N, Whitlow W G, et al. “Towards industrial internet of things: crankshaft monitoring, traceability and tracking using RFID”, *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 2016, 41, 66–77.
12. Cao Y, Li W, Song W, et al. “Collaborative material and production tracking in toy manufacturing”, *Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE 17th International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design (CSCWD)*, 2013, pp. 645–650.
13. <https://www.empoweredautomation.com/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-fourth-industrial-revolution-pdf#:~:text=The%20Fourth%20Industrial%20Revolution%20Risks%20and%20Benefits&text=While%20it%20promises%20enhanced%20productivity,cybersecurity%20threats%2C%20and%20privacy%20issues.>
14. Lukman L, I., Soo-Hyun P., Isa A. I., “A New IoT Architecture for a Sustainable IoT Adoption”, *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology Research*, Vol. 5, Issue 2, pp: 204-208, Month: April - June 2017, Available at: www.researchpublish.com.
15. Isa A. I., “Skills rather than just degrees”, Publisher: University Press, ISBN: 9789789409594, NLN Code: NLN-XAHR1NR1RLGDLZ0M, <https://virtuall.nln.gov.ng/resource/NLN-XAHR1NR1RLGDLZ0M>.
16. Isa A. I., “Cybersecurity Initiatives For Securing A Country”, Publication details: Ibadan University Press PLC 2022, ISBN: 9789789409310, <https://opac.fuhsi.edu.ng/cgi-bin/koha/opac-detail.pl?biblionumber=171>.
17. Isa A. I., Muhammad A. B., “Bidirectional People Counters as a Catalyst for Smart Cities in the Technological Singularity Era”, *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, Volume 11, Issue 10, pp. 193-196, October 2024, www.jetir.org.
18. <https://www.rowse.co.uk/blog/post/whats-the-difference-between-industry-4.0-and-industry-3.0>.
19. Isa, A., I., Muhammad, A., B., “Theoretical perspectives on digital globalization: A critical review”, *Edelweiss Applied Science and Technology*, Vol. 8, No. 6, Pp. 4384-4388, 2024, DOI: 10.55214/25768484.v8i6.2938.
20. <https://www.empoweredautomation.com/5th-industrial-revolution#:~:text=5th%20Industrial%20Revolution%20Inventions&text=Advanced%20Human%2DMachine%20Interfaces%3A%20New,between%20humans%20and%20digital%20systems.>
21. Sarafadeen L. L., Livingston S. A., & Muhammad A. B. (2024). How the Third and Fourth Industrial Revolutions Differ. In *Global Journal of Research in Engineering & Computer Sciences* (Vol. 4, Number 6, pp. 114–118). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14497184>.
22. M. A. Baballe, M. I. Bello, Z. Abdulkadir, “Study on Cabot’s Arms for Color, Shape, and Size Detection”, *Global Journal of Research in Engineering & Computer Sciences* ISSN: 2583-2727 (Online) Volume 02| Issue 02, pp. 48-52, Journal homepage: <https://gjrpublication.com/journals/>, 2022.
23. M.A. Baballe, et al., “Design and Implementation of the hand Pick and Place Cobots' Arms for Color Detection”, 3rd International Conference on Applied Engineering and Natural Sciences <https://www.icaens.com/>, July 20-23, 2022, Konya, Turkey.
24. Huang S, Guo Y, Zha S, et al. “A real-time location system based on RFID and UWB for digital manufacturing”, *workshop[J]. Procedia CIRP*, 2017, 63, 132–137.